

STRENGTHENING UNDERGROUND REINFORCED CONCRETE STRUCTURES USING EXTERNALLY BONDED CARBON FIBRE-REINFORCED POLYMER SHEETS

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ABSTRACT

Globally, most of our infrastructures have deteriorated or reached the end of their intended lifespan due to changes in usage or structural degradation. As a consequence, they are in urgent need of repair, strengthening, rehabilitation, or replacement. Canada is no exception and is facing challenges due to the condition of its concrete infrastructure, which requires immediate attention. For instance, the underground core network in Calgary's downtown, which comprises approximately 2735 manholes and 476 transformer vaults, exhibits severe deterioration. While replacing these underground structures with new ones would be ideal; however, it is not an option as it is often financially and operationally impractical due to their location and continuing usage. Therefore, repairing and strengthening these structures using Externally Bonded Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer (EB-CFRP) sheets is crucial for the safety of Calgarians. Hence, this paper aims to investigate the feasibility and effectiveness of using EB-CFRP sheets to restore the original flexural capacity of these deteriorated structures.

KEYWORDS: Anchorage; Externally Bonded; Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer; Deterioration; Rehabilitation; Strengthening.

INTRODUCTION

The civil engineering and construction industry has faced unexpected challenges in the last few decades due to the state of repair of concrete infrastructures worldwide, and Canada is no exception. Reinforced Concrete (RC) structures are susceptible to deterioration for various reasons, including poor design, corrosion of the reinforcing steel, lack of maintenance, increased traffic volumes, fires, earthquakes, low-quality material, and accidental overloading. As a result, such deteriorated concrete structures must be replaced, strengthened, or rehabilitated to be kept in good condition and/or extend their service life. Deterioration negatively affects safety and increases the maintenance costs of our infrastructure. Over time, deteriorated reinforced concrete structures lose their strength. While it is advisable in some situations to replace such structures with new ones, this is often financially and operationally impractical. Instead, strengthening the deteriorated structures with additional reinforcements could be the solution. There is a substantial financial cost to replace, repair, or maintain the existing structures. Still, failing structures also pose a significant threat to public safety if not properly managed. Thus, deterioration and damage of RC structures is a never-ending problem that incites civil engineers around the world to continuously seek durable, robust, practical, efficient, and economical retrofitting and strengthening techniques using advanced high-performance materials to repair deteriorated and deficient structures to reduce the financial costs above and improve our infrastructure's service.

Traditional rehabilitation and strengthening methods, such as adding new structural elements, enlarging sections, post-tensioning of steel tendons/plates, spraying concrete etc., have several drawbacks, such as complexity of the application, time consumption, and lack of durability^[1].

Fibre Reinforced Polymer (FRP) systems have been used in different configurations (sheets, strips, plates, bars) using various techniques for strengthening RC structures to restore or increase their capacity. Some FRP strengthening techniques could be more effective; however, their cost-effectiveness and applicability are significant and could govern their use due to overall maintenance budget constraints and the structure's location to be repaired. Many researchers reported significant increases in the strength and stiffness of Carbon FRP strengthened RC members. The commonly used technique related in principle to this project to provide additional flexural strength for damaged or

deficient RC structures is the Externally Bonded (EB) CFRP sheets applied on the tension side of flexural concrete members.

Externally Bonded Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer (EB-CFRP) sheets have been developed as an effective rehabilitation technique to address some of the drawbacks of the traditional strengthening methods. The key advantages of the CFRP strengthening system over traditional structural materials and systems comprise a high strength-to-weight ratio (ten to fifteen times greater than steel), lightweight (one-fifth to one-seventh that of steel of equivalent area), easy installation and handling, and corrosion resistance. Several experimental studies have investigated the flexural and shear improvement and the failure modes of FRP-strengthened RC beams. These researchers identified failure mechanisms that might reduce the strengthening impact of structures using FRP retrofits. Delamination of the FRP, debonding of concrete layers, and peeling due to shear cracks are some of the failures that have been documented. These failures happen at much lower loads than the theoretical strength of the retrofitted beams^{[1][2][3][4][5]}. Several other investigations focused on enhancing the flexural capacity of RC beams using EB-CFRP sheets or plates with different configurations (i.e. type of FRP, length, thickness, number of layers, and area) and the internal reinforcement ratio. Moreover, it was observed that the common failure mode of RC beams strengthened with CFRP plates or sheets is due to FRP peeling off, and this can be prevented by providing end plate anchorage and long unanchored plate lengths^[6]. In addition, it was determined that debonding failure would influence the performance of strengthening beams and should be considered during the design process^[7].

BACKGROUND PROBLEM

The ENMAX Power Corporation, a leading electricity provider in Alberta, Canada, is facing tremendous challenges with Calgary's downtown underground core network that, comprised of approximately 2735 Manholes and 476 Transformer Vaults, are aged over 40+ years and showing severe signs of deterioration. While replacing these underground structures with new ones would be ideal; however, it is not an option because it is often financially and operationally impractical due to their location and continuing usage. Therefore, repairing and strengthening these structures is crucial for the safety of all Calgarians. Inspection of these underground structures revealed major concrete cracking, spalling at several locations and signs of steel corrosion. Figure 1 shows the typical cracks in some of the wall specimens. Furthermore, Ground Penetration Radar (GPR) scanning indicated that the arrangement and location of the main flexural reinforcement differed from the original design drawings. The reinforcement was located closer to the compression side than the tension side, as observed at the end of the specimen. Thus, the specimens were deemed deficient in flexural and required repairing the cracks and flexural strengthening. Furthermore, strengthening these structures presents a remarkable solution, ensuring the creation of long-lasting and highly durable structures prioritizing Calgarians' safety and livelihoods. Therefore, it was proposed to use externally bonded (EB) Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) sheets to strengthen the specimen in flexure. Figure 2 shows the cross-section and reinforcement details of the specimens as per the construction drawings and the as-built specimen determined from the GPR scanning.

Figure 1. Major Flexural Cracks

This study evaluates the feasibility and effectiveness of strengthening deficient RC wall specimens using EB-CFRP sheets to restore their original flexural capacity and increase their strength. The

motivation is driven by the fact that the EB-CFRP strengthening system could hold the key to extending the service life of deficient RC structures and is the ideal choice to retrofit deteriorated underground RC structures. Therefore, using EB-CFRP sheets is expected to overcome the challenges of replacing underground RC structures and resolve the crisis facing ENMAX.

Figure 2. Cross-section and reinforcement arrangements

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

The experimental program comprises testing three wall specimens cut from dismantled deteriorated underground walls of manholes. One wall specimen acted as a control un-strengthened, and two were strengthened with EB-CFRP sheets. All specimens were tested under quasi-static monotonic four-point loading until failure. Based on the study's findings, the feasibility and effectiveness of the EB-CFRP technique in increasing and restoring the flexural capacity of damaged underground RC structures were established.

Details of Tested Specimens

All specimens have a rectangular cross-section (400×220 mm) with a total length of 1950 mm, span centre-to-centre of the supports of 1850 mm and main flexural reinforcement of 2-20M. Before anything else, the cracks in specimens S#1 and S#2 were repaired with epoxy injection. The repaired Specimen #1 was cut into two specimens, one served as a control un-strengthened (specimen S1-R-C), and the other was strengthened with an EB-CFRP sheet and marked as S1-R-S. After testing the control specimen to failure, it was decided to repair its failure crack with epoxy injection before being strengthened with EB-CFRP sheets and marked as S1-R-C-S. Specimen #2 was taken from a different but similar manhole, and its major crack was repaired with epoxy injection and then strengthened with EB-CFRP sheets (specimen S2-R-S). S1 denotes specimen from Manhole #1, S2 denotes specimen from Manhole #2, R denotes for repair, C denotes for control, and S denotes strengthened. Note different anchorage systems were applied at the ends of the EB-CFRP sheets for the three strengthened specimens to investigate the appropriate system that avoids debonding failure. Details are presented in the section Anchorage System.

Materials

Concrete and Steel

A compressive strength test on six drilled concrete cores was performed to determine the in-place compressive strength of the hardened concrete in the specimens. The core tests assess an existing structure's strength and evaluate structural capacity. The results indicated the in-place concrete compressive strength equals 34.72 MPa. Schmidt Hammer test was also conducted on the specimens to estimate the compressive strength of the concrete; the results indicated concrete compressive strength of 32.7 MPa. According to the construction drawings, the specific yield strength of the reinforcing steel bars is 400 MPa.

Strengthening Materials

The EB-CFRP sheets used in this study is SikaWrap® Hex-230 C, a unidirectional carbon fibre fabric. The CFRP sheet has a thickness of 0.38 mm, a tensile modulus of 74,700 MPa, a tensile strength of 801 MPa, and an elongation at rupture of 1.01%. The CFRP sheets were bonded to the specimen using Sikadur®-300 epoxy adhesive. In addition, Sikadur®-330 primer was applied to the concrete surface before installing the CFRP sheets to create a better bond between the concrete surface and the CFRP

sheet. Voids and irregularities on the surface of the specimens were filled with putty (Sikadur®-31 Hi-Mod GelCA). Before applying the EB CFRP sheets, the main crack on three sides of the specimen was sealed using high-performance grade epoxy acrylate anchoring adhesive (AnchorFix®-2020). Then, the crack was injected with Sikadur®-35 Hi-Mod LV epoxy adhesive.

PREDICTION OF SPECIMENS FLEXURAL CAPACITY

The flexural resistance of the unstrengthened RC specimens was determined as simply supported members per the CSA/CAN-A23.3-19^[8]. However, the flexural resistance of the strengthened RC specimens was determined according to the FRP Building Code CSA/CAN-S806^[9].

Original Flexural Capacity of the Specimens (S1-R-C)

Based on the actual construction drawing of the underground walls of the manholes, the existing reinforcement in a strip of 400 mm width is 2-20M with a clear concrete cover to the tension side of 40 mm (as shown in Figure 2 a). The specified concrete compressive strength is 30 MPa, and the steel yield strength is 400 MPa. The cracking moment (M_{cr}) based on the gross moment of inertia and the ultimate nominal moment of resistance ($M_{n.c.u.}$) of the control unstrengthened specimen (S1-R-C) as per the construction drawings is equal to 11.4 kN·m and 41.31 kN·m, respectively. The ultimate nominal concrete shear resistance ($V_{n.c.u.}$) equals 75.86 kN. However, according to the as-built specimen (Figure 2 b), the cracking moment based on the gross moment of inertia and the ultimate nominal moment of resistance is equal to 10.6 kN·m (i.e. 34.38 kN load) and 16.44 kN·m (i.e. 53.32 kN load), respectively,

S1-R-C-S

Due to the considerable difference in the arrangement of the main flexural reinforcement between the original construction drawings and the actual state of the underground built RC manholes, testing the control specimen before strengthening the other specimens was crucial to understanding the effect on the overall flexural behaviour of placing the reinforcement on the wrong side. The experimental results of the control specimen indicated that the specimen acted as a plain concrete beam (more details can be found in the Results and Discussion section). Therefore, to reconfirm the results and take advantage of the failed control specimen, a decision was made to repair the failure crack by epoxy injection and then strengthen it with EB-CFRP sheets. Assuming the tension steel is on the wrong side (more on the compression side) and contributes to the flexural capacity, the maximum area of CFRP sheets that can be provided to avoid shear failure is 193.8 mm², equivalent to an ultimate nominal moment of resistance ($M_{n.c.s.}$) of 46.55 kN·m (i.e. 150.97 kN load). As a result, specimen S1-R-C-S was strengthened with two layers of CFRP sheets with a width of 255 mm and a length of 1750 mm.

S1-R-S and S2-R-S

After confirming that the control specimen (S1-R-C) is acting as plain concrete to avoid shear failure, the maximum provided area of CFRP for the specimens S1-R-S and S2-R-S is 278.16 mm² and 277.4 mm², respectively, resulting in an ultimate nominal moment of resistance after strengthening ($M_{n.s.}$) equals to 46.48 kN·m (i.e. 150.75 kN load) and 46.36 kN·m (i.e. 150.37 kN load), respectively. As a result, specimen S1-R-S was strengthened with three layers of CFRP sheets with a width of 244 mm and a length of 1750 mm. However, specimen S2-R-S was strengthened with two layers of CFRP sheets with a width of 365 mm and a length of 1750 mm.

CRACK REPAIR PROCEDURE

The crack injection repair process of the specimen shown in Figure 3 includes the following steps:

- First, cleaning the inside interface surface of the crack with compressed air.
- Sealing the crack with the Sika AnchorFix®-2020 epoxy adhesive all around the three sides of the specimen before epoxy injection.
- Bonding with the Sika AnchorFix®-2020 the T-shaped ports for crack injection at 4 inches intervals along the length of the crack.
- Curing the sealed specimen for 24 hours.
- Filling the cracks with Low Viscosity epoxy (Sikadur®-35 Hi-Mod LV) through the T-shaped ports.
- Curing the epoxy injected cracked specimen for 24 hours before installing the EB-CFRP sheets.

(a) Sealed crack and installed T-shape ports

(b) Injecting the crack with epoxy

Figure 3. Repairing the cracks using epoxy injection

STRENGTHENING PROCEDURE

Figure 4 shows the following steps performed to strengthen the concrete specimens with EB-CFRP:

Surface Preparation

For proper bonding, a concrete surface must have the correct Concrete Surface Profile or CSP that allows for visual determination of the surface roughness. CSP is a standardized measure of surface roughness defined by the International Concrete Repair Institute (ICRI). One of the surface preparation methods suggested by Sika is surface grinding with diamond pads by removing high spots on the concrete surface and any other surface contaminants^[10]. Typical recommendations by Sika specify CSP-3 to CSP-5 as per the ICRI guidelines.

All specimens' surface was grinded with a diamond disk. However, after consulting with ENMAX, it was decided that using grinding with diamond tools would create a lot of dust that requires a capable dust collector to be used on-site inside the manholes, which is a closed, confined area that is not an onsite allowed option due to safety concerns with the electrical cables. Therefore, a minimum surface grinding preparation was performed to at least remove any surface contaminants. Compressed air and a vacuum cleaner were used to remove dust and loose particles. Then, the irregularities, blowholes and voids in the concrete surface were filled with putty (Sikadur[®]-31 Hi-Mod Gel^{CA} mixed with dried sand) to smoothen the concrete surface.

Priming the Concrete Surface

The primer (Sikadur[®]-330) was spread on the concrete surface using a paintbrush. The purpose of applying the primer is to create a better bond between the concrete and the CFRP sheet.

Application of the EB-CFRP Sheets

The SikaWrapHex230C CFRP sheets were cut to each specimen's desired length and width. The CFRP sheets were saturated with Sikadur[®]-300 epoxy on both sides before applying to the specimen. According to the manufacturer's recommendations, epoxy was applied to the concrete surface while the primer was still sticky. The CFRP sheet was bonded at the tension side of the specimen and smoothed out with gloved hands. A ribbed roller was used to work out any irregularities or entrapped air pockets underneath the sheets to ensure the sheets were in complete contact with the concrete surface. An additional layer of epoxy was applied to the first CFRP layer within 60 minutes before applying it to the second layer / or third layer as per the manufacturer's recommendations.

The strengthening procedure described above was carried out in ideal laboratory conditions, where the specimen was positioned horizontally, and the strengthening process was implemented from top to

bottom. However, the field installation will be fairly similar because the manhole walls, which are accessed from within, are oriented vertically. Thus, despite the differences in orientation, the field installation procedure will closely resemble the laboratory procedure.

Figure 4. Strengthening Process

Anchorage System

Three different anchorage systems were used at the ends of each specimen. The aim of selecting different anchorage systems is to demonstrate the most appropriate system for preventing premature failure due to debonding of the CFRP sheet at its end.

S1-R-C-S

An additional 100 mm wide \times 255 mm length CFRP sheet was applied at both ends of the longitudinal 1750mm CFRP sheets, as shown in Figure 6 a.

(a) Anchorage System for S1-R-S

(b) Anchorage System for S2-R-S

Figure 5. Anchorage system for specimens S1-R-S and S2-R-S

S1-R-S

The anchorage system at the end of the EB-CFRP sheets consists of grooves (15 mm × 15 mm) cut transversely in the concrete at both ends, and then two CFRP sheets were placed in the longitudinal direction and into the grooves at both ends. Next, a 10 mm diameter Glass FRP rebar was placed on the top of the two CFRP sheets and inserted into the grooves. Lastly, an additional 100 mm wide × 244 mm length CFRP sheet was applied at both ends. The anchorage system for S1-R-S is shown in Figure 5 a and Figure 6 b.

S2-R-S

A 100 mm wide × 365 mm length aluminum plate was placed on the top of the CFRP sheets at both ends of the 1750mm CFRP sheet. 1.5 inches long Hilti nails were used to anchor the aluminum plates to the concrete surface, as shown in Figure 5 b and Figure 6 c.

Figure 6: Strengthening arrangement of the specimens

TEST SETUP AND INSTRUMENTATIONS

The specimens were simply supported on a roller and pinned supports, with a span between the support of 1850 mm and tested under static monotonic loading up to failure. The load was applied to a spreader beam clamped to a 1000kN capacity actuator through an MTS universal swivel head and platen of an MTS hydraulic actuator operating under displacement control mode at a constant loading rate of 1mm/min. The specimens were loaded at four-point bending with 617 mm spacing between the two concentrated point loads acting along the entire width of the specimen. The load was transferred to the specimen at the loading points, with one loading point being a pinned roller and the other being a roller. All specimens were instrumented to monitor their behaviour during testing by measuring the vertical deflection at midspan using Linear Strain Conversion devices (LSCs). The CFRP sheet was instrumented with conventional foil Strain Gauges (SG) (with a resistance of 120 Ω and a gauge length of 10 mm) along its length (1750 mm). The strain gauges were installed at the location of the two-point loads and the edge of the CFRP sheets in each specimen. In addition, crack widths were measured using a crack comparator, and their patterns were marked on both sides of the concrete specimens during testing at predefined load increments of 5 kN. Data were automatically collected and electronically recorded using a data acquisition system. Typical test setup and instrumentation are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Test Setup

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The representative mode of failure for each specimen is shown in Figure 8. The load-midspan deflection curves are given in Figure 9.

S1-R-C

The first hairline flexural crack was observed at midspan at a load of 10.5 kN. No further cracks formed. Very shortly, the load increased quickly, and the specimen failed at an ultimate load of 32.7 kN, corresponding to a midspan deflection of 0.59 mm, as shown in Figure 9 after which the load dropped to about 9.5 kN and almost remained constant until a decision was made to unload the specimen at a midspan deflection of 11.54 mm. The specimen failed in flexure at the major large crack midspan, as shown in Figure 8 a.

S1-R-C-S

Figure 8 b depicts the failure mode of specimen S1-R-C-S; an intermediate large crack caused debonding and CFRP rupture at an ultimate load of 63.1 kN. The first crack was observed at a load of 51 kN, with an average midspan deflection of 7.81 mm. The premature rupture was likely due to the poor surface preparation resulting in debonding caused by the irregularities and roughness of the concrete surface, which was sanded instead of grinded. Furthermore, as shown in Figure 9, the highest mid-span deflection was 10.22 mm. Compared to the control specimen S1-R-C, the appearance of the first crack was delayed, and the deflection decreased. The midspan deflection was reduced as the flexural stiffness increased due to the CFRP strengthening. In addition, the ultimate load was 93% greater than specimen S1-R-C.

S1-R-S

Shear failure was observed in specimen S1-R-S simultaneously with the anchorage failure at the end of the CFRP sheets, as shown in Figure 8 c, due to the low shear capacity of the specimen. The first crack was observed at a load of 45 kN. The failure was sudden, and the diagonal crack increased the vertical separation of the concrete, inducing additional peeling stress at the CFRP-concrete interface. The shear crack initially appeared across the entire concrete depth at 112 kN, meaning that it is possible that the CFRP sheets increased the specimen's shear resistance and that the specimen's actual shear resistance was considerably lower than the theoretical value. The ultimate load of (121.91 kN) was increased by 273% compared to specimen S1-R-C. The average midspan deflection at the ultimate load was 19.28 mm, as shown in Figure 9.

S2-R-S

Anchorage failure was observed in specimen S2-R-S due to the insufficient embedment length of the Hilti nails. The first crack was observed at a load of 56 kN. Similar to S1-R-S, the shear crack appeared at a lower applied load of 82-86 kN, suggesting increased shear resistance from the EB-CFRP sheets. The anchorage failure was more apparent than in specimen S1-R-S (the nails had ejected from the concrete and plate). The ultimate load of specimen S2-R-S (99.14 kN) was increased by 202.7% compared to specimen S1-R-C. The average midspan deflection at 99.14 kN load was 15.58 mm, as

shown in Figure 9. Generally, the deflection increased gradually with the load as strengthening the specimens increases their stiffness and ductility behaviour. As a result, the maximum enhancement achieved compared to the control unstrengthened specimen is 273%, roughly the same as the original load capacity of the tested specimen.

Figure 8. The failure mode of the specimens

Figure 9. Load-midspan deflection for S1-R-C, S1-R-C-S, S1-R-S, and S2-R-S

In general, it was noted that strengthening with EB-CFRP sheets delayed the first crack and enhanced the load capacity and reduced deflections. In addition, smaller crack widths and closer flexural cracks were observed through the loading process in the strengthened specimens.

COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND THEORETICAL FLEXURAL CAPACITY

The theoretical flexural strength results for the control specimen were predicted as per CSA/CAN-A23.3-19 provisions^[8]. In contrast, the flexural resistance for the strengthened specimens using EB-CFRP sheets was predicted according to the CAN/CSA S806-201^[9] code. The experimental and theoretical results are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Strengthening Layout, Experimental and Theoretical Results of the Tested Specimens

Specimen ID#	CFRP strengthening layout and areas	Results		
		Experimental	Theoretical	
		P_{exp} (kN)	M_{theo} (kN·m)	P_{theo} (kN)
S1-R-C	NONE	32.7	16.44*	53.32
S1-R-C-S	2 layers (255mm × 1750mm) 198 mm ²	63.1	46.55**	150.97
S1-R-S	3 layers (244mm × 1750mm) 278 mm ²	121.91	46.48**	150.75
S2-R-S	2 layers (365mm × 1750mm) 277 mm ²	99.14	46.36**	150.37

* CAN/CSA A23.3-19

** CAN/CSA S806-2012

The result of specimen S1-R-C dedicated that the specimen acted as a plain concrete beam, and the reinforcements on the compression side are not contributing. S1-R-C failed experimentally at 32.7 kN, which is very close to the theoretical cracking load of 34.38 kN based on the gross moment of inertia or the 31.46 kN based on the transformed moment of inertia with the steel contributing on the wrong side. This failure load of 32.7 kN is also lower than the ultimate theoretical load of the as-built specimen, with the steel on the wrong side contributing (53.32 kN); this confirms that specimen S1-R-C acted as a plain concrete specimen. Moreover, the theoretical ultimate shear capacity was calculated ($V_r = 77.58$ kN) to be considered while strengthening the specimens to avoid shear failure. After that, the strengthening of the specimens was based on the results obtained from S1-R-C, dedicating that all specimens act as plain concrete and require strengthening. The amount of CFRP sheets needed was based on the maximum amount of CFRP sheets that can be applied to prevent shear failure ($V_n < V_r$).

The ultimate theoretical load of specimen S1-R-C-S is 150.97 kN (based on the as-built condition with the contribution of the steel on the compression side to the flexural capacity), strengthened with an area of 193.8mm² CFRP sheets, which is much greater than the ultimate experimental load (63.1 kN). Even if the comparison is made with the ultimate theoretical load of 106.76 kN determined based on the as-built condition without the contribution of the steel on the compression side. However, the results were expected since this specimen was cracked and repaired twice. Moreover, this specimen was strengthened while it was beneath the actuator, and thus the strengthening procedure was done without any surface preparation.

Specimen S1-R-S strengthened with an area of CFRP sheets of 278.16 mm² failed experimentally at an ultimate load of 121.91 kN smaller than the ultimate theoretical load (150.75 kN), the maximum load that can be achieved at preventing shear failure. The difference between experimental and theoretical ultimate load values might be due to the minimum surface preparation of the concrete surface. However, the surface preparation on site is not easy since these specimens are underground, and it is challenging to do a complete surface preparation due to safety concerns inside a confined space. Furthermore, the specimen was already cracked with a major flexural crack (which affects the strength of the tested specimen even though this crack was repaired with epoxy injection).

Specimen S2-R-S strengthened with 277.4 mm² CFRP sheets failed experimentally at an ultimate load of (99.14 kN) smaller than the ultimate theoretical load (150.37 kN). However, this specimen failed due to anchorage failure. Thus, it is not rational to compare the theoretical and experimental results unless we increase the embedment length of the Hilti nails, which was the reason for the anchorage failure.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the efficiency of using EB-CFRP sheets to restore the original flexural capacity of the deteriorated underground reinforced concrete structures. Three specimens were repaired and strengthened using EB-CFRP and epoxy injection, while only one was repaired with epoxy injection and served as a control unstrengthened specimen. Furthermore, a different anchorage system was applied to each specimen. Therefore, based on the results of this experimental study, the following conclusions can be made:

- Repairing severely flexural-damaged specimens using EB-CFRP sheets and epoxy injection restored their original flexural capacity
- The utilization of the EB-CFRP strengthening system enhances the load and deflection at the point of initial cracking when compared to the un-strengthened. These findings align with previous research conducted on the subject.
- Shear failure in the concrete simultaneously with the anchorage failure was observed. Thus, more testing is required to choose the most suitable anchorage system

As expected, there is clear evidence that CFRP strengthening has significantly improved the flexural capacity of the repaired flexural deficient specimens. However, in the meantime, no preferable anchorage system has been recommended to ENAMX to prevent brittle failure, debonding of the CFRP sheets or anchorage failure until more testing is conducted, such as using a larger embedment length of the Hilti nails or gradually reducing the area of the CFRP at the ends, or investigating the use of mechanically-fastened CFRP plate. More testing is ongoing to determine the suitable anchorage system for this field application.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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